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BADDIY MATN XUSUSIYATLARI VA UNING TARJIMASIDAGI QIYINCHILIKLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola badiiy matnning xususiyatlari va tarjimon badiiy asarni tarjima qilishda e'tibor berishi kerak bo'lgan mezonlarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Yozuvchi chinakam so'z ustasi sifatida hamkasblar olomonidan ajralib turish, yangi gaplar aytish bilan birga kitobxonlar e'tiborini abadiy savollarga qaratish uchun yangi badiiy ifoda vositalarini topishga harakat qiladi. San'at asarlarining manbai fantaziyaning erkin faoliyati bo'lib, u o'z xayoliy narsalarni yaratishda tabiatning o'zidan ham erkinroqdir. Jamiyat adabiy matnlarni boshqalarga qaraganda uzoqroq saqlaydi. San'at asarlari ming yillar davomida yashashi mumkin. Bu deyarli abadiy adabiyot asarlarini tarjima qilish uchun ajratilgan vaqt beqiyos qisqa.

Kalit so'zlar: badiiy matn, tekstologiya, manba tili, maqsadli til, stilistik mazmun, mantiqiy matn.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА И СЛОЖНОСТИ ЕГО ПЕРЕВОДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена исследованию особенностей литературного текста и критериям, на которые переводчик должен обращать внимание при переводе художественного произведения. Писатель, как истинный мастер слова, старается найти новые средства художественной выразительности, чтобы выделиться из толпы коллег, привлечь внимание читательской аудитории к вечным вопросам, сказав при этом что-то новое. Источником произведений искусства является свободная деятельность фантазии, которая в создании своих воображаемых предметов даже свободнее самой природы. Общество хранит художественные тексты дольше, чем какие-либо другие. Произведения искусства могут жить тысячи лет. Время, отведенное на перевод этих почти вечных произведений литературы, несравненно мало.

Ключевые слова: художественный текст, текстология, исходный язык, язык перевода, стилистическое содержание, логический текст.

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THE PECULIARITIES OF LITERARY TEXT AND DIFFICULTIES OF ITS TRANSLATION

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of the features of a literary text and the criteria that a translator should pay attention to when translating a work of art. The writer, as a true master of the word, tries to find new means of artistic expression in order to stand out from the crowd of colleagues, to draw the attention of the readership to eternal questions, while saying something new. The source of works of art is the free activity of fantasy, which in the creation of its imaginary objects is even freer than nature itself. Society keeps literary texts longer than any other. Works of art can live for thousands of years. The time allotted for the translation of these almost eternal works of literature is incomparably short.

Key words: literary text, textology, source language, target language, stylistic content, logical text.

Nowadays, the notion of "literary text" is utilized in a broad, indefinite, effusive meaning. An artistic text is considered as a complex text in the linguistic classifications of the context (structure parameter), a work of artistic style (functional-style parameter), prepared text (parameter readiness), non-fixed (algorithmic parameter), soft (concept explication parameter), descriptive with features of deontological and axiological texts which is functional-pragmatic parameter [2, 217].

The notion of "literary text" includes a subjective side from a psycholinguistic point of view. In this case, given category is understood by some researchers, especially V. P. Belyanin, as a personal author's interpretation of reality [10, 168].

Determining the parameters of a literary text from the standpoint of communication theory, researchers, for example, V.G. Admoni, V.A. Maslova, V.A. Pishchalnikov, distinguish in this concept, along with subjective characteristics, the aspect of verbalization of the author's intention. In this case a literary text can be defined as a sensorial notional understanding of the world as a speech statement, "a communicatively directed verbal work" arising from a specific (egocentric) inner state of the artist [1, 194].

In some of literary investigations, "text" and "work" are comprehended similarly. Although, regarding linguists, these words should be differentiated. Despite a huge quantity of definitions, a literary "text" has constant features that give opportunity to distinguish it from a "work".

Firstly, the text is comprehended as a more common notion. In this case, A.L. Grishunin argues that it is crucial to split the text from the work, in general, artistically. The text is only a collection of graphic signs, but it's not a work, to a great extent a conventional structure that presents this work and makes the reader to sense it. The text and the work should be made appropriately. According to this definition, we have to emphasize the fact that a text is a kind of sequence of characters which the reader can perceive permanently, because a work is a type of reception of the text that is quite personal for every reader. This gives us chance to talk about the variety of text and work according to their graphic recording and structure [10, 67].

The other point of view about the difference between the text and the work is based on the correlation of work with definite idea. In consequence, a work is considered to be a text from the view of textology, combined by content and form and generally varying. As a result, a work is known as a sort of challenging content, appearing from the text [8, 173].

Therefore, the work is considered to be the content which the reader producing while comprehending the text. V.A. Lukin thinks that the work is linked with the text, so there is the widely used term "the text of the work". It's needless to say that the content is imbued with the text of a work of art. First of all, if the text is a work of art, then it must differ in its figurative and descriptive level, content, idea, concept and meaning, and at the same time it must be related to them in some way [9, 28].

Moreover, the text of a work is a complex system of heterogeneous speech units: it includes lexical and phraseological levels, a layer of allegories, intonational and syntactic, rhythmic, and phonetic aspects.

Secondly, artistic and speech means have independent expressive significance, and therefore are "burdened" with meaning. Thirdly, the verbal material of the work bears the burden of the subject-figurative structure of the text, that is essential in content and includes author's opinion with the highest accuracy. That's why, the text is linked by implication with the area of ideology and content. Therefore, we can deduce that the literary work does not deliver the author's opinions clearly.

The text and the work are connected as a process and a result, as something common, endlessly lasting. To understand the work (result), you need to refer to the production process - the text. A number of researchers argue that the concept of the text has expanded to the boundaries of the culture. The text is a cultural phenomenon, a generalized model of the world that constitutes an integral facet of culture.

A translation, without expressing the full content of the original, reflected one of its possible definitions, and society, developing, becomes able to see new facets of the great original work and requires a new translation. A literary text often turns out to be multi-layered: deep levels of ideas, symbols, images appear behind the surface level of the plot, which are difficult to transfer to a new cultural and aesthetic environment, which makes it almost impossible to preserve the entire volume of artistic means used to reveal the content plan.

Generally, in comparison to a text, literary text has a number of special features, the most essential of which is the really active usage of various tropes and notions of speech. They also include:

1. Fiction (i.e., the fact that the world depicted in the text is fictitious, fictional), the content of inner world of the work.
2. It is obligatory to note that a literary text is a compound system of means of the native language, and furthermore, it is a symbolic system of a literary text that the reader must decipher for understanding the text.
3. Extra meaning included into the integrity of the work of art.
4. Connectivity of all parts of the text.
5. Transformation of the poetics of the word, strengthening the importance of vocabulary and updating the level of vocabulary.
6. Determining the implicit meanings of the subtext.
7. Changing the meaning of a literary text and connections between texts, an intertextual approach.

It is clear that, one of the important reasons why a literary text differs from any other text is that the real world is presented figuratively in them. As a human has a logical and figurative system of thinking the texts can be divided into artistic and non-artistic. Scientific documents and other non-fiction works are connected with logical ways of thinking and logical perception of the world, but fiction literature deals with figurative thinking and a human's ability to understand the environment figuratively.

Therefore, it is relevant to talk about the fact that the logical texts are existed and they link to the logical reflection of the world and tend to convey real data. However, artistic texts connected with the figurative reflection of the world and current complex delivery of different types of intellectual, emotional and aesthetic data. They can emotionally impact on the reader.

The variety of literary texts gives us opportunity to talk about the difference in the ways of forming texts. Logical texts are written for the purpose of communication, while literary texts are written for the purpose of impact. Of course, any literary text communicates something, but this is not the main purpose of its writing. If for a logical text the communication of facts is the main function

and, therefore, the main goal of its creation, then for a literary text it is only a method of impacting the reader. The function related to an impact in a literary work is not satisfactory because it is concentrated only on the creation of an emotional and sensible attitude, to some episodes, facts, events. In many occasions, the writer not just tries making the reader rejoice or suffer emotionally, but do it for an appropriate goal. Even in a poetic description of nature, the author seeks to evoke the emotional state in the reader that he experienced himself, using a poetic form so that the reader can share with him his emotional standing, which arose not in general, but for some reason.

Literary texts differ from logical texts not only in the purpose of creation, but also in the nature of the transmitted data, because in fiction text, intellectual, and emotional, and aesthetic information is normally sent. It is normal to demand unique methods of delivering data. The rational, emotional and aesthetic impact on the recipient is crucial for sending this data.

Different types of language elements are needed to achieve such an impact. This goal can be reached with the help of rhythmic organization of the text, phonosemantics, lexical semantics, grammatical semantics, and many other means.

Information in a fiction source, unlike a logical text, can be transferred in so many words, or it can be implied with the help of all sorts of allegories - allegories, symbols, illusions, etc. An allegory is a conditional transmission of an abstract concept or judgment through a specific image (for example, a wolf is the personification of greed a fox is cunning, etc.).

One of the distinguished features of the literary text is the expected scale of activity of the reader, his implication in the creative works. In logical texts the role of the receiver is diminished to the understanding of arguments, in literary work the writer sometimes refers to the life of the person to whom the text is directed, reckons on the emergence of definite associations in the reader, on a certain level of assumption. It becomes easy due to the choice of the kind of recital, the attendance of number 1 of the narrator in the text, and the level of allocution of the text.

Literary translation is a special area of translation activity and is a written translation of works of art from one language into another. The basic complication of translation the literary text is not even in reporting the meaning, but in the ability to depict the unique writer's style of the text, aesthetics, variety of language elements and the atmosphere, humor, character and mood appropriate for the text.

We read a lot of foreign literature. But how often do we read books by foreign writers in their original language? Just imagine how many literary works would be inaccessible to a wide range of readers if there were no translators of literary texts who are “guides” to the fascinating world created on the pages of books.

The implementation of the literary translation of prose or poetry is, without exaggeration, an art, a creative activity. Therefore, among translators, literary translation is considered one of the most difficult. It cannot be compared with business translation, where you need to convey the expected information in standard phrases. It is not like simultaneous translation, in which it is important to react quickly and formulate a thought precisely, often to the harm of the fluency and composition of the sentence. Literary translation is also fundamentally different from legal or scientific and technical translations, which require the utmost accuracy, almost verbatim. In a literary translation from any language, the atmosphere of the plot and the unique author's style should be preserved to the maximum extent.

Literary translation has a number of features and, accordingly, difficulties.

It is pointed out that artistic texts comprise a huge number of stylistic features, the conveying of which shows high quality of intelligence, imaginative notions and unique professionalism from the interpreter. The most regular means of expressive devices in literature are metaphors, epithets, comparative phrases, neologisms, repetitions (lexical, phonetic, morphemic, etc.), dialecticisms, professionalisms, realities, toponyms, speaking names, names and surnames, etc.

Particular difficulties arise when the source and target languages belong to different cultures. For example, the works of Arabic authors are replete with quotations from the Koran and allusions to its plots. An Arabic reader recognizes them quite easy like an educated European reader who recognizes inscriptions to the Bible or ancient legends. In translated version, these expressions don't remain understandable to the Europeans. The translated versions of fiction genre are also difficult to

understand for people from Europe, for instance, comparing a nice looking woman with a camel sounds funny. However, it is normal for people of Arabic origin to treat women in this manner. And the translation of the fairy tale "The Snow Maiden" will be challenging for people who came from Africa or India due to the fact that there is no snow in these areas. Therefore, for translator cultural differences much more difficult to convey than differences in languages.

The modern approach to text translation is not recognized by translators because of the simple logic of equality of impressions. The contemporary reader's perceptions of original and translation should coincide. Modern translation does not give the reader information that the text is modern, but, on the contrary, using special translation methods, it tries to show how ancient it is. Such an outstanding translator as K. Chukovsky believes that each era has its own style, and in order to show the flavor of the era of the thirties of the last century or such words characteristic of the nineties as moods, experiences, searches, supermen, it is necessary to use certain vocabulary [4, 117].

The translator can reflect the era with the help of lexical, morphological and syntactic archaisms. So he creates an archaic stylization.

Stylization is not a full assimilation of the target language to the language of the past times, but only the use of archaisms in the text. In the original text, you can find various stylistic devices that are used to make the text more vivid and expressive. The same emotional effect can be reached by copying the device of the original or creating a different stylistic device in the translation. This principle of stylistic compensation according to K.I.Chukovsky when not a metaphor should be conveyed by a metaphor, but a comparison by a comparison, but a smile with a smile or a tear with a tear [5, 293].

According to the translator, the function of the stylistic device in the text plays an important role in comparison with the form. This means that the translator is given a certain freedom of action when grammatical means of expression can be transmitted lexically and vice versa. A stylistic phenomenon that cannot be described in the translation is omitted and the translator creates a different image in another place in the text, thereby resuming the meaning of the translation where it is most convenient, but with a similar stylistic focus.

Stylistic content of a text or statement includes stylistic meanings, and requires taking into account the peculiarities of the culture and life of the people in the translation, which is carried out in the process of changing the content plans and expressing the language units of the source text in the translated text. Considering the most common types of lexical transformations in the classification of L.S. Barkhudarov, it is worth noting that in lexical substitutions, individual lexical units of the source language are used, replaced by lexical units of the target language and equivalents that are not found in their dictionary, since they are used in isolation and have different value compared to original language units.

Most often there are three cases of lexical replacement, such as concretization, generalization and replacement, based on causal relationships.

The replacement of a word with a broad meaning by a word with a narrower meaning occurs in linguistic concretization due to differences in the composition of the two languages, the absence of a lexical unit in the target language with the same broad meaning as the transmitted unit of the source language, stylistic differences, or grammatical requirements. As a result, the abstract English word "thing" is essentially pronominal and translated by concretization: thing, object, deed, fact, case, circumstance, work, being, and so on.

In general, while translating from English to Russian, terms with broad meanings like man, woman, person, or creature are replaced with particular appropriate names or nouns like elderly man, soldier, bystander, hostess, dog, cat, and so on. This is especially crucial when translating fiction, when using terms with an abstract, generalized meaning too frequently is improper. However, contextual specification is caused by elements peculiar to this context, most typically stylistic concerns such as the necessity for phrase completion, the need to minimize repetition, and the aim to attain more figurativeness and clarity [3, 237].

In addition to the aforementioned translation methods and procedures, there is also the very uncommon search for a functional equivalent. In classical categorization, there is no such mechanism

of translation. It's utilized, for example, when a work's text contains amusingly frivolous phraseological units that are common in native English speakers' speech. Generally, while translating, only their meaning is explained generally, since in this case the phraseological unit is based on different images. Some linguists call this method "equivalence".

- *Your nose is bleeding, lower, lower, lower...*
- *Ваш магазин открыт час, другой, третий...*[4, 201].

This expression “your nose is bleeding” is used when they want to say that someone's trousers are not buttoned up. In Russian, the metaphor of the nose is replaced by the metaphor of an open store.

An extremely important conclusion follows from the fact that in a literary text we cannot think about the whole notion from the number of the parts. If we translate each component of the text we cannot reach the understanding of the whole text. And therefore the translator has to do exact investigation in order to maintain the logical and chronological sequence of the parts which is depicted by the writer and connected to the translator.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

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